

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in Guangdong, China

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Sixty isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* of different virulence were inoculated into 46 rice varieties. Results

showed that varietal resistance to bacterial blight may be grouped into three categories: broad spectrum, nonbroad spectrum, and no resistance.

Most introduced cultivars belonged to the broad spectrum group (see table). Varieties Tsai-Ye-Ching 8, Foo-Bao-Ai 22, Jiao-Jin-Fung 5, Qiu Er Ai 1-3, Teng Pu-Ai, Tetep, and Zenith belonged to the nonbroad spectrum group. Improved plant type and high-yielding

varieties such as IR8, Zhen-Zhu-Ai 11, Quang-Liu-Ai 4, Quang-Er-Ai No. 5-3, and Jing-Gong 30 belonged to the no resistance group.

To incorporate bacterial blight resistance into breeding materials, the most promising results will be obtained by using varieties with broad-spectrum resistance and virulent strains of the predominant pathogenic group 4 of Guangdong province for screening tests. ■

Rice varietal resistance to 60 isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in China.^a

Type of resistance	Variety	Origin	Disease scale	Resistant (%)		Moderate (%)		Susceptible (%)	
				HR	R	MR	MS	S	HS
I	3303	China	HR	100.00					
	IR2161	Philippines	HR-R	98.33	1.67				
	IR2061-522-6-9	Philippines	HR-R	93.33	6.67				
	G.E. 456	USA	HR-R	93.33	6.67				
	VPR-70-3-7	—	HR-R	91.38	8.62				
	DV85	India	HR-R	86.67	13.33				
	IR26	Philippines	HR-R	64.41	35.59				
	BG-35-2	Sri Lanka	HR-MR	81.67	15.00	3.33			
	IR30	Philippines	HR-MR	28.37	70.00	1.67			
	Hai-ching 130	China	HR-MS	81.30	13.60	1.73	3.37		
	IR36	Philippines	HR-MS	73.37	23.33	1.67	1.67		
	IR32	Philippines	HR-MS	50.94	39.62	7.55	1.89		
	IR22	Philippines	HR-MS	68.33	25.00	1.67	3.33	1.67	
	IR1545	Philippines	HR-MS	23.33	68.33	3.33	5.00		
	IR28	Philippines	HR-MS	7.85	68.63	13.72	9.80		
	Hai 42	China	HR-MS	61.67	28.33	3.33	1.67		5.00
	II	Lan Xian 1	China	HR-HS	43.33	46.67	3.33	5.00	0
1388		China	HR-HS	38.33	40.00	8.33	0	5.00	8.33
74-105		China	HR-HS	33.33	46.67	5.00	8.33	1.67	5.00
Fei-Yan (076)		Philippines	HR-HS	28.33	26.67	15.00	10.00	6.66	13.33
Unnamed (Zhung San)		China	HR-HS	15.00	41.67	21.67	10.00	3.33	8.33
2150		China	HR-HS	5.00	38.33	25.00	11.66	8.33	11.66
IR661		Philippines	HR-HS	1.67	21.67	41.67	11.67	15.00	8.33
Ai-Tong-Zhu		China	R-HS		25.00	48.33	15.00	5.00	6.67
Xai-Tan-Gu 4882		Indonesia	R-HS		25.00	43.00	20.00	8.33	3.33
Tsai-Ye-Ching 8		China	R-HS		23.73	40.68	16.95	10.17	8.47
Foo-Bao-Ai 22		China	R-HS		23.73	28.81	30.51	3.39	13.55
Tetep		IndoChina	R-MS		10.00	38.33	33.33	8.33	10.00
BTO-MO-3-3			R-HS		18.97	41.38	29.31	5.17	5.17
Teng-Pu-Ai		China	R-HS		8.33	18.33	46.67	18.33	8.33
Jiao-Jin-Fung 5		China	R-HS		11.86	27.12	30.51	18.64	11.86
IR24		Philippines	R-HS		9.09	38.18	30.91	10.91	10.91
Qiu-Er-Ai 1-3		China	R-HS		5.00	31.67	38.33	16.67	5.00
Guai-Chao-2		China	R-HS		5.00	20.00	40.00	20.00	15.00
Er-Bai-Ai		China	R-HS		1.67	11.67	60.00	15.00	11.67
co 22		India	R-HS		1.67	20.00	41.67	23.33	13.33
Zenith (dwarf)	USA	R-HS		1.75	5.26	29.82	31.58	31.58	
Zenith (purple)	USA	R-HS		1.67	11.66	36.67	38.33	11.56	
III	Tadukan	Philippines	MR-HS			17.24	46.55	20.69	15.51
	Bao-Tai-Ai	China	MR-HS			5.00	48.33	26.67	20.00
	9101	China	MR-HS			5.00	55.00	16.67	23.33
	Guang-Er-Ai 5-3	China	MR-HS			3.00	26.67	28.33	41.67
	Jing-Gong 30	China	MR-HS			1.67	23.33	46.67	28.33
	IR8	Philippines	MR-HS			3.33	33.34	43.33	20.00
	Zhen-Zhu-Ai 11	China	MS-HS				30.00	51.67	33.33
	Quang-Liu-Ai 4	China	MS-HS				3.33	30.00	66.67

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.